

Discrete-time Luenberger observer design for Lithium-ion battery state-of-charge with stability guarantee

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ABSTRACT

State-of-charge (SOC) estimation is particularly important as it provides information about the remaining energy capacity of the battery, allowing for better planning and utilization. Accurate SOC estimation is challenging because it cannot be directly measured from the battery. Instead, it is estimated by analyzing measurable variables such as current and voltage. To address this challenge, a discrete-time observer-based SOC estimation approach is proposed in this paper. This approach utilizes a second-order equivalent circuit model and a piecewise linear approximation to represent the relationship between SOC and open circuit voltage (OCV). The proposed observer-based approach utilizes these models to estimate the SOC with assured asymptotic stability under specific assumptions to simplify the design process. Simulations in Python are conducted to evaluate the performance of the designed observer. In the simulations, the SOC estimation under various conditions, such as model uncertainty, disturbances, and measurement noise, is also covered. In addition, three different observer gains are considered in the simulations. Lastly, simulation studies indicate that the estimated SOC values converge to the real SOC values, with some different behavior depending on the regarded situations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the development of electrical vehicles (EVs) has been rapidly growing, which has led to the widespread utilization of batteries as energy storage devices. As technology continues to advance, the demand for higher energy density and faster charging capabilities in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) has become increasingly vital for the widespread adoption of electric vehicles. LIBs are recognized as the most preferred alternative for EVs due to their numerous benefits, including their high energy storage capacity and long lifespan. [1]-[4]. When using LIBs, monitoring and regulating the charge and discharge operation is crucial since the batteries must be ensured to function as intended, e.g., prevent overcharging and overdischarge, and have a long lifespan [5]-[7]. The LIBs are then complemented with an electronics module known as a battery management system (BMS) to manage these tasks [8]-[12].

The battery monitoring and regulation function in the BMS involves an important variable called state-of-charge (SOC) [3], [13]-[15]. However, this variable cannot be measured directly by a sensor. Instead, the SOC must be estimated through measurable variables, i.e., current and (terminal) voltage—the electrical potential difference between two battery polarities. An algorithm for estimating the SOC employs a mathematical model of the battery that accommodates a nonlinear dynamic behavior [16]. A popular model used for it is the equivalent circuit model (ECM). ECM is an electrical circuit dynamic model as an analog to the nonlinear dynamic behavior of a battery [17]. In addition, it models several essential properties of the battery, including internal resistance, resistive-capacitive (RC) time constant, open-circuit voltage (OCV)—the battery's electrical potential difference between two polarities that are disconnected from any load—and nominal capacity [18], [19]. Additionally, ECM is so popular for SOC estimation in BMSs because it meets the computational capacity constraints of BMSs [20].

Many SOC estimation algorithms have been proposed in [21], [22]. However, many of them lack stability guarantees as well as exact rules for determining tuning gains. Therefore, in this study, we propose an observer design based on one first proposed by Luenberger [23] for LIBs SOC estimation with a guarantee of stability from a control theory perspective. In addition, we present some numerical simulations involving the appearance of model uncertainties and disturbances that exist in real-world applications. The preliminary work of this study has been presented and published in [24].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the battery model, covering the ECM description and the nonlinearity relationship between OCV and SOC. The main results, comprising the observer, stability analysis, numerical simulations, and discussion, are presented in section 3. Lastly, we summarize our study in section 4.

2. METHOD

2.1. Equivalent circuit model

In this study, we use an equivalent circuit model (ECM) with two RCs. This model is well-known as a 2-RC ECM or second-order ECM. Figure 1 illustrates this model. The ordinary differential equation of the 2-RC ECM is presented in (1), (2), (3), and (4), where time $t \geq 0$ and \dot{V}_1 , as an instance, denotes the first time-derivative of V_1 .

$$\dot{V}_1(t) = -\frac{1}{R_1 C_1} V_1(t) + \frac{1}{C_1} I(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{V}_2(t) = -\frac{1}{R_2 C_2} V_2(t) + \frac{1}{C_2} I(t) \quad (2)$$

$$V_T(t) = V_{OC}(\xi(t)) - R_S I(t) - V_1(t) - V_2(t) \quad (3)$$

Where $V_{OC}(\xi(t))$, or simply V_{OC} , is a nonlinear function representing the relationship between OCV and SOC. While the dynamic equation of the SOC is represented in (4), where Q_ξ is the battery capacity [Ah] and η is Coulombic efficiency—it describes how efficiently a battery transfers electrons during charging and discharging. This form is well-known as a continuous-time version of Coulomb counting.

$$\dot{\xi}(t) = \frac{\eta}{3600 \cdot Q_\xi} I(t) \quad (4)$$

The other parameters and variables of the 2-RC ECM are explained as follows:

- I denotes the battery current [A]. It has positive polarity when charging and negative polarity when discharging.
- V_T denotes the terminal voltage [V]. It represents the real voltage available for utilization from the battery. The terminal voltage is measured across the terminals when a load is attached to the battery.
- (R_1, C_1) and (R_2, C_2) represent the first and second RC models of the 2-RC ECM, respectively. These relate to the diffusion dynamics [25].
- R_S is also internal resistance [Ω] of the the 2-RC ECM.

Figure 1. 2-RC equivalent circuit model

Furthermore, an equivalent 2-RC ECM model can be expressed in (5) and (6). This model has a state variable $x(t)$ and an output $y(t)$ which is nonlinear. Note that $(x(t))$ consists of $V_{OC}(\xi(t))$, which is generally a nonlinear function. It will be elaborated on in the following subsection.

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t), \\ y(t) = C(x(t)) + Du(t) \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Where

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = \begin{bmatrix} V_1(t) \\ V_2(t) \\ \xi(t) \end{bmatrix}, \\ y(t) = V_T(t), \\ u(t) = I(t), \\ A = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{R_1 C_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{R_2 C_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{C_1} \\ \frac{1}{C_2} \\ \frac{1}{3600 \cdot Q_\xi} \end{bmatrix}, \\ C(x(t)) = V_{OC}(\xi(t)) - V_1(t) - V_2(t), D = -R_s \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

A discrete-time version of the 2-RC ECM can be realized using Euler's discretization, as indicated in (7) and (8) with the same model parameters A, B, and D as in (6), where $h > 0$ is sampling period [s] and $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ is the sample sequence.

$$\begin{cases} x(k+1) = (I + hA)x(k) + hBu(k) \\ y(k) = C(x(k)) + Du(k) \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Where

$$\begin{cases} x(k) = \begin{bmatrix} V_1(k) \\ V_2(k) \\ \xi(k) \end{bmatrix}, \\ y(k) = V_T(k), \\ u(k) = I(k), \\ C(x(k)) = V_{OC}(\xi(k)) - V_1(k) - V_2(k), \\ I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

In real-world applications, obtaining the exact model of a battery is a difficult task. This is because of the presence of model uncertainty, which corresponds to the gap between the known model and the actual/real battery model. Besides, the existence of measurement noise at the output and disturbances that affect the input may not be avoided. The model uncertainty and disturbances are accommodated in the following model.

$$\begin{cases} x(k+1) = (I + h(A + \Delta_A(k)))x(k) + h(B + \Delta_B(k))(u(k) + w(k)) \\ y(k) = C(x(k)) + (D + \Delta_D(k))(u(k) + w(k)) + v_1(k) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Where Δ_A , Δ_B , and Δ_D represent the gaps between the battery's known and true parameters. $w(k)$ and $v_1(k)$ represent the input disturbance and output measurement noise, respectively.

2.2. Relationship between open circuit voltage and state-of-charge

As described in the previous subsection, the OCV as a function of SOC, $V_{OC}(\xi)$, is generally a nonlinear function. This nonlinear function can be represented using polynomials. Instead, in this paper, we approximate it with a piecewise linear function. We adopt it from Xu *et al.* in [26]. The piecewise linear function of $V_{OC}(\xi)$ is depicted in Figure 2. The curve in Figure 2 is plotted based on the linear function (10), whose parameters are listed in Table 1. In this paper, we assume the known and the real $V_{OC}(\xi)$ function is exactly the same.

$$V_{OC}(\xi) = a_i \cdot \xi + b_i \quad (10)$$

Figure 2. An approximation of the nonlinear relationship between OCV and SOC with a piecewise linear curve

Table 1. Piecewise linear function parameters of $V_{OC}(\xi)$

i	SOC	a_i	b_i	i	SOC	a_i	b_i
1	$0 \leq \xi < 0.1$	0.59	3.5052	6	$0.5 \leq \xi < 0.6$	0.6	3.4199
2	$0.1 \leq \xi < 0.2$	0.49	3.5188	7	$0.6 \leq \xi < 0.7$	0.82	3.2864
3	$0.2 \leq \xi < 0.3$	0.39	3.5397	8	$0.7 \leq \xi < 0.8$	0.8	3.3004
4	$0.3 \leq \xi < 0.4$	0.28	3.5728	9	$0.8 \leq \xi < 0.9$	0.9	3.2232
5	$0.4 \leq \xi < 0.5$	0.36	3.5416	10	$0.9 \leq \xi < 1$	0.99	3.1364

3. MAIN RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Proposed observer

Considering (7), A consists of (R_1, C_1) and (R_2, C_2) . Suppose we have a sampling period and battery parameters that satisfy the following properties:

$$0 < h \frac{1}{R_1 C_1} < 1$$

$$0 < h \frac{1}{R_2 C_2} < 1$$

Therefore, we propose the observer as given in (11):

$$\begin{cases} \bar{y}(k) = C(\bar{x}(k)) + D\bar{u}(k) \\ \bar{x}(k+1) = (I + hA)\bar{x}(k) + hB\bar{u}(k) + h\bar{K}(y(k) - \bar{y}(k)) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where

– $\bar{u}(k)$ and $y(k)$ are obtained from sensors, where $\bar{u}(k) = u(k) + v_2(k)$ and a couple $(u(k), y(k))$ is represented in (9).

– $\bar{x}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{V}_1(k) \\ \bar{V}_2(k) \\ \bar{\xi}(k) \end{bmatrix}$ is the estimated state, where $\bar{\xi}$ is the estimated SOC.

– $\bar{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \kappa \end{bmatrix}$ is the observer gain that satisfies the condition: $\kappa > 0$ such that $0 < h \kappa \bar{a}_{max} < 1$, where $0 < h < 1$. In addition, \bar{a}_{max} is the maximum coefficient of the linear lines of V_{OC} that refers to value a_i in Table 1.

Figure 3 shows a flowchart of the state-of-charge estimation using our observer. Additionally, it is worth noting that the proposed observer (11) the model with known parameters (7). Besides, to avoid confusion for readers, it is also worth noting that the model in (9) is for numerical simulation purposes. In addition, regarding the properties of (R_1, C_1) and (R_2, C_2) stated above, it is reasonable since the parameters of batteries found in various papers satisfy those properties.

Figure 3. SOC estimation flowchart

3.2. Stability analysis

In this subsection, the stability proof of the proposed observer is elaborated. Now, recall $\bar{V}_{OC}(\xi)$ in (10) and $y(k)$ in (7). Since $V_{OC}(\xi(k)) = \bar{a}_i(k)\bar{\xi}(k) + \bar{b}_i(k)$, hence we have the following:

$$C(\bar{x}(k)) = \bar{H}(x)\bar{x}(k) + \bar{b}_i(k) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\bar{H}(k) = [-1 \quad -1 \quad \bar{a}_i(k)] \quad (13)$$

In order to reduce the complexity of observer design, we apply the following assumptions:

- For all $k \leq 0$, $\xi(k)$ and $\bar{\xi}(k)$ can be not equal, but both are always on the same piece of a linear line of the $V_{OC} - SOC$ curve. For example, $(\xi, \bar{\xi}) = (0.31, 0.35)$ is on the same piece of a linear line, while $(\xi, \bar{\xi}) = (0.31, 0.55)$ is not on the same piece of a linear line.
- $\Delta_A(k)$, $\Delta_B(k)$, and $\Delta_D(k)$ are all zero. In other words, the real battery parameters are assumed to be known exactly.
- It is assumed that there is no disturbance and noise, i.e., $w(k)$, $v_1(k)$, and $v_2(k)$ are also zero.

Note that these assumptions reflect that the actual battery used for stability analysis is identical to the model battery employed in the observer, namely the model in (7). Let define the estimation error $e_{\bar{x}}(k)$ (14):

$$e_{\bar{x}}(k) = x(k) - \bar{x}(k) = \begin{bmatrix} e_{\bar{x}1}(k) \\ e_{\bar{x}2}(k) \\ e_{\bar{x}3}(k) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Regarding the assumption above that ξ and $\bar{\xi}$ are on the same piece of a linear line of the OCV-SOC curve, we have the following.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{\bar{x}}(k+1) &= (1+hA)e_{\bar{x}} - h\bar{K}(y(k) - \bar{y}(k)) \\ &= (1+hA)e_{\bar{x}} - h\bar{K}\bar{H}(k)e_{\bar{x}}(k) \\ &= (1+hA - h\bar{K}\bar{H}(k))e_{\bar{x}}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Next, motivated by the structure of the nonlinear observer gain in [16], i.e., $\bar{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \kappa \end{bmatrix}$, we consider

the following facts:

- The sampling period h is less than 1s, i.e., $0 < h < 1$.
- Entries of matrix A satisfy $0 < \frac{1}{R_1 C_1} < 1$ and $0 < \frac{1}{R_2 C_2} < 1$.
- The coefficient \bar{a}_i satisfies $0 < \bar{a}_i \leq \bar{a}_{max} < 1$.

Now, consider the following Lyapunov function candidate (16) and its forward difference (17).

$$V(k) = e_{\bar{x}1}(k)^T e_{\bar{x}1}(k) > 0, \forall e_{\bar{x}1}(k) \neq 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V(k) &= V(k+1) - V_1(k) \\ &= \left(1 - h \frac{1}{R_1 C_1}\right)^2 e_{\bar{x}1}(k)^2 - e_{\bar{x}1}(k)^2 \\ &= \left(\left(1 - h \frac{1}{R_1 C_1}\right)^2 - 1\right) e_{\bar{x}1}(k)^2 < 0 \text{ provided that } 0 < h \frac{1}{R_1 C_1} < 1 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

These facts imply that $e_{\bar{x}1}(k)$ approaches 0 as k approaches infinity. In addition, we can use a similar analysis to prove $e_{\bar{x}2}(k)$ also approaches 0 as k approaches infinity, if it satisfies $0 < h \frac{1}{R_2 C_2} < 1$.

Now, consider the first Lyapunov function candidate expressed by (18) as follows:

$$\tilde{V}(k) = e_{\bar{x}3}(k)^T e_{\bar{x}3}(k) > 0, \forall e_{\bar{x}3}(k) \neq 0 \quad (18)$$

in addition, its forward difference is given as (19):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \tilde{V}(k) &= \tilde{V}(k+1) - \tilde{V}(k) \\ &= (e_{\bar{x}3}(k) + h\kappa e_{\bar{x}1}(k) + h\kappa e_{\bar{x}2}(k) - h\kappa \bar{a}_i e_{\bar{x}3}(k))^2 - e_{\bar{x}3}(k)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

in the previous description, we know that $e_{\bar{x}1}(k)$ and $e_{\bar{x}2}(k)$ approach 0 as k approaches infinity; hence, we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \tilde{V}(k) &= (e_{\bar{x}3}(k) - h\kappa \bar{a}_i e_{\bar{x}3}(k))^2 - e_{\bar{x}3}(k)^2 \\ &= \left((1 - h\kappa \bar{a}_i)^2 - 1\right) e_{\bar{x}3}(k)^2 < 0 \text{ provided that } 0 < h\kappa \bar{a}_i < 1 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

to be more generally applicable, the condition becomes $0 < h\kappa \bar{a}_{max} < 1$. It completes the stability analysis.

3.3. Numerical simulation and discussion

Simulations run adopt LIB parameters in [27], for $R_S, (R_1, C_1)$ and (R_2, C_2) , and in [28], for Q_ξ . All simulations regard that the Coulombic efficiency η is 1 (see (4)). These are shown in Table 2. We utilize Python 3.12.1 for the simulations.

In the first simulation, we show how the situation represents a simplified case as described in the stability analysis above. In this situation, the real and estimated SOC values are on the same piece of a linear line of the V_{OC} curve; the initial conditions of real SOC and estimated SOC values are 0.98 and 0.91, respectively. Besides, the discharge current $u = I$ is set to a constant value, i.e., $-0.49A$. Three values of the observer gain κ are used for comparison of the performance. Figure 4 shows the simulation result. We can notice that the higher observer gain gives a faster estimated SOC approach to the real SOC. Nevertheless, all estimated SOC values tend to provide zero estimation error. Next, it is of interest to see how observers could perform in more practical scenarios.

Table 2. Battery parameters

	Ω	F	Ah
R_1	0.015	C_1	1000
R_2	0.0015	C_2	2500
R_S	0.024	Q_ξ	4.9

Figure 4. SOC estimation result based on the simplified situation meets the asymptotically stable guarantee

In the second simulation, we set the initial conditions of real SOC and estimated SOC are 0.98 and 0, respectively. Another difference from the previous simulation is that we use the disturbance w and the noise (v_1, v_2) , which are the normal random numbers whose maximum amplitude is 0.001. Each normal random number that represents the disturbance and noise is generated uniquely. Figure 5 shows the simulation result. All estimated SOC values tend to reach the real SOC with the same speed as in the first simulation. However, we could identify that the higher observer gain implies a higher distortion amplitude. In addition, at about $2800 - 3000s$ there are jumps (drops and lifts) in the estimated SOC values. It might relate to the nonlinearity of the relationship between OCV and SOC (see Figure 2). However, the important fact is that this indicates there is an error in SOC estimation due to noisy sensor data.

The third simulation includes the uncertainties Δ_A, Δ_B , and Δ_D . These values vary by a maximum 10% of the known parameters (A, B, C). It is implemented by, for example, $\Delta_B = B \times 0.1S_\Delta$, where S_Δ is sine wave with the frequency is $5 \times 10^{-5}Hz$. This simulation result is shown in Figure 6. The result is similar to the previous situation, except that, compared to Figure 5, there is a shift between the real SOC line and the estimated SOC line. It is noticeable at about $2800s$ in the area where the estimated SOC values jump.

Next, we consider using a different profile of the current discharge. It is in the form of pulse width modulation (PWM) whose frequency, duty cycle, and amplitude are $1 \times 10^{-3}Hz$, 10%, and $-4A$, respectively. It is called the multiple step test (MST) [29]. The other situations in this simulation are the same as the previous one. The simulation result is depicted in Figure 7. We could notice there are jumps in every occurrence of sudden discharge current. However, the shape is not as similar as the jumps in the previous figures. In this simulation, it appears that there are additional overshoot and undershoot properties that usually appear in the step response of a control system. However, it indicates that the observer failed to provide a perfect SOC estimation when a sudden discharged current occurs.

Figure 5. SOC estimation result using the model suffers from disturbance and noise

Figure 6. SOC estimation result using the model suffers from disturbance, noise, and model uncertainty

Figure 7. SOC estimation result using the model suffers from disturbance, noise, and uncertainty with a PWM discharge current

4. CONCLUSION

A discrete-time Luenberger observer-based to estimate a Lithium-ion battery's state-of-charge is presented. Some assumptions are used in the stability analysis in order to prevent complexity in the observer design. The observer has an asymptotically stability guarantee. Multiple simulations are conducted to assess the observer's performance. The simulations also consider the situation that corresponds to a realistic situation, such as the unknown initial value of the real battery's state of charge as well as the appearance of disturbance, noise, and model uncertainties. Based on the simulation results, some challenging problems could be considered for further research. One aspect is to utilize a higher observer gain to quickly achieve the actual SOC and a lower observer gain to minimize distortion.

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